

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING PRACTICAL RESEARCH WRITING

Christian F. Buyoc, LPT ¹
Ramon M. Bantugan, PhD ²

¹*Pagalangang National High School, Department of Education, Dinalupihan, Bataan, Philippines*

²*Bataan Peninsula State University - Main, Commission on Higher Education, Balanga City, Bataan, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI), along with the tools built around it, such as Grammarly, ChatGPT, Quill Bot, Jenni AI, and DeepSeek, continuously asserts dominance in the field of education and research. However, there are limited studies that explore the relationship between the teacher and this educational technology. Thus, to equip teachers who station the frontline amidst the emergence of this technology, the study aimed to shed light on the roles of AI in Practical Research writing classes and the opportunities and limitations that it presents for the teachers and students alike. By considering the nature of the study, a convergent parallel design was employed. The quantitative phase utilized a survey questionnaire, while interview questions sought answers for the qualitative phase. The numerical data were analyzed through descriptive statistics, while thematic data analysis was employed to decode the implications in the interview responses. The quantitative findings revealed that AI's role is modifying and augmenting instruction. On the other hand, the qualitative findings not only highlighted the benefits of AI in aiding educators in developing the research writing skills of the learners but also the limitations, which involve the issues that concern the user and the technology. The study recommends leveraging AI to enhance research instruction while ensuring ethical use, equitable access, and sustained teacher development.

Keywords: *AI, Artificial Intelligence in Education, Mixed-Methods Research, Practical Research Writing, Research Instruction,*

INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has shown that it can be a valuable tool for productivity and work efficiency in various fields, such as academics and research. Quill Bot, Semantic Scholar, Mendeley, Scite, and many other AI are now at the forefront of academic or scientific research. Consequently, AI has significantly impacted education and linguistics in recent years, due to its ability to understand and respond through Natural Language Processing (NLP) and process data through Machine Learning (Churi et al., 2022).

AI has been found to support both teachers and students in research instruction. It helps researchers design, analyze, and write their studies (Altmäe et al., 2023), while student researchers use AI for writing evaluation, text generation, translation, and grammar checking (Alharbi, 2023). The ability of AI to provide personalized feedback, encourage student involvement, and enhance grading efficiency makes it valuable for teaching (Dong, 2023; Kim & Kim, 2022). Similarly, AI facilitates the customization of instruction (Thang et al., 2022) and is useful in teaching grammar, content, and writing skills (Visaltanachoti et al., 2021; Kawinkoonlasate, 2021). These studies establish a common ground where AI is an effective instruments that can help students and researchers improve their papers. However, there is a gap in investigating the direct benefits and limitations that it presents to the teacher and lesson delivery.

Amidst these benefits, the risks and limitations of AI utility remain a concern for educators. For instance, the originality and accuracy of the students' work are affected when AI tools are integrated into teaching (Misra & Chandwar, 2023). There is a tendency to copy and paste AI-generated text without modifying or adding their own ideas. Another concern is the preparedness of the schools and their personnel to regulate AI use. The Government AI Readiness Index 2022 reports that the Philippines was ranked 54th among the 181 countries (Rogerson et al., 2022). In the educational context, this shows the schools' capacity to properly cater to the evolving landscape of education because of technology, particularly AI.

These concerns highlight the importance of fully understanding AI in the context of its utility and integration practices to avoid malpractice (King, 2023). As Churi et al. (2022) emphasized, writing or producing research outputs could be challenging, especially for students who are still learning the basics of research writing. Paired with a lack of training in using AI as a tool in writing, ethical concerns may arise. In line with this, Borenstein and Howard (2020) proposed solutions concerning ethics that will enable schools to use AI more responsibly in teaching and learning.

With these potential opportunities and limitations of AI in teaching, the researcher was motivated to investigate the roles of AI-based tools in research writing instruction for several reasons. There was a need to conduct more research on the subject, particularly

within the local context. The rise of several AI-based tools that students and teachers use in teaching and learning piqued the researcher's interest in investigating their roles in the instructional process. Primarily, it helps the research writing teacher be more effective in the classroom. In addition, it is currently the most timely and relevant subject in language teaching. On the other hand, this study is essential in language education because it will expand the knowledge of how AI might be used as an educational technology to improve the teaching of writing in an English as a Second Language (ESL) setting. It could also help other researchers in the field as they explore this area of investigation. Overall, the research will fill the gap in the existing body of knowledge on the subject and present opportunities for further studies.

Research Questions

The study aimed to investigate the roles of AI in Practical Research Writing in the Senior High Schools of Bataan during the School Year 2024-2025.

Specifically, the study sought to find answers to the following questions:

1. How may the roles of Artificial Intelligence in teaching be described in terms of:
 - 1.1. substitution
 - 1.2. augmentation
 - 1.3. modification; and
 - 1.4. redefinition?
2. What are the pedagogical opportunities and limitations of using Artificial Intelligence and their effect on the students?
3. How do the roles of Artificial Intelligence relate to its pedagogical opportunities and limitations?
4. How may the findings of the study be used as a training plan for improving instructional practices?

METHODOLOGY

Design, Methods, and Techniques of the Study

The study employed a mixed-method research design to answer the research questions adequately. Specifically, a convergent-parallel design was employed. This method was used in gathering distinct but related data on the same phenomenon. The convergent-parallel approach is a concurrent methodology that entails the collection of both qualitative and quantitative data, which was consequently integrated and subjected to comparisons.

This approach enabled the study to obtain adequate answers to the research questions for several reasons. Primarily, the first research question required a quantitative approach since it aimed to identify and describe the common practice of technology integration among the research teachers in the province. Moreover, the second research

question called for a qualitative approach, for it aimed to thoroughly elaborate on how certain AI integration practices were beneficial or limiting to the teachers. Given that the first and second research questions sought complementary rather than identical answers, it was more suitable to use a convergent design.

Population

The study population included practical research writing teachers in the senior high schools of Bataan. There were sixty-five (65) respondents in the quantitative phase who were selected with the help of their immediate supervisors. All the research teachers from every senior high school were included, despite their small number. For the qualitative phase, fourteen (14) participants were interviewed. In total, there were seventy-nine (79) teachers who took part in the study. There was no sampling done in the selection of the participants since the teachers who are qualified is extremely low in number.

Research Instrument

The quantitative aspect of the study used survey questionnaires. A questionnaire is designed to gather the respondents' experiences, opinions, attitudes, and insights to satisfy the research questions. This helped the pre-survey identify the AI-based tools commonly used in practical research instruction. On the other hand, the primary survey form consisted of four sections corresponding to each level of the SAMR model. Each level had nine (9) statements that described the nature and extent of AI application in that category. The respondents selected their answers by choosing the following options: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree.

To gather the qualitative data, a semi-structured interview was used. This form of interview is a combination of structured and unstructured interviews. A set of questions was prepared, but additional questions could be asked during the interview process. This instrument enabled the exploration of different opportunities and limitations in using AI-based tools for practical research writing, without compromising the relevance of the data. The unstructured questions enabled the researcher to see trends and patterns. In summary, semi-structured interviews allowed for focus without restricting participants from sharing their experiences or perceptions.

Construction and Validation of Instrument

Due to the novelty of the subject, the researcher constructed an instrument to gather data. The survey questionnaire for the quantitative phase was constructed using the SAMR model, other related literature, and the research objectives as guides. Since the first research question aims to identify the nature of use and the extent to which AI is used in research instruction through the SAMR Model, the statements in the Likert scale reflect how AI is used for substitution, augmentation, modification, and redefinition. Further, the statements for each category were based on the literature review of the utilization of AI in teaching, academic writing, and research. Likewise, the qualitative interview questionnaire was also constructed based on the literature review and research objectives. Nine general questions centered on the advantages and disadvantages of

using an AI tool in teaching practical research. The questions were carefully written to acquire the target responses and achieve the research objective number two, but not to the extent of leading the respondents to specific answers.

In validating the instruments, three subject matter experts checked whether the qualitative and quantitative questionnaires aligned with the research objectives. The researcher sought the assistance of two Master Teachers and one Head Teacher with a master's degree in Language Education from Dinalupihan, Bataan, for the instrument validation. The researcher sought permission from the persons involved and provided a copy of the paper and the questionnaires. After the agreed-upon time, the researcher and the experts conducted consultations regarding the revisions and improvements that needed to be made on the questionnaire. The majority of the comments were about the specificity of the terms, construction, and phrasing of the indicators or statements, and the addition of other indicators that could help in acquiring the target responses. Further, the face validity and correctness of grammar were also scrutinized to ensure the language accuracy of the questionnaires. Lastly, the researcher revised the questionnaire based on the feedback and resubmitted it for final checking.

In testing the reliability of the questionnaire, a pilot quantitative survey questionnaire was administered after the instrument validation. Due to the limit on the potential respondents for the study, 10 research teachers from Grade 10, SHS research teachers from other provinces such as Pampanga, and Research Project Teachers were engaged. The primary criterion for the alternative respondents is that they must be teaching research and employ the use of AI for the research instruction. Cronbach's alpha was used for the results of the pilot quantitative survey questionnaire, as it assesses the degree of reliability found in survey replies. Further, it was used to gauge the internal consistency or reliability of several items or ratings.

The researcher sought the assistance of a statistician in using the software Cronbach alpha (v1.0.7) in Free Statistics Software (v1.2.1), which can be accessed through this link: https://www.wessa.net/rwasp_cronbach.wasp. The responses of the respondents were entered into the software, and results were generated. Findings are categorized based on the following scale: Less than 0.5 is unacceptable, > 0.5 is poor, > 0.6 is questionable, > 0.7 is acceptable, > 0.8 is good, and > 0.9 is excellent. The analysis of data showed that the Cronbach Alpha of the pilot test results is 0.9389, which is interpreted as excellent. This suggested that the items in the questionnaire were reliable.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure for the study was composed of two processes: a survey for the quantitative part and an interview for the qualitative part. Prior to data gathering, the respondents and participants were approached with the objectives of the study and informed of the consent. For the quantitative part of data gathering, a survey questionnaire was distributed to the respondents through Google Forms. A survey was a data collection procedure that gathered data among the identified sample and population by asking questions through a survey questionnaire. The use of Google Forms was to address concerns regarding the respondents' availability to participate in the study.

Concurrently, interviews were conducted to gather the qualitative data. Depending on the availability of the participants, several modalities were employed, such as in-person interviews, phone calls, or virtual meetings. The live interaction between the researcher and the participants allowed for the clarification and elaboration of responses. In all these modalities, the interaction was audio-recorded for the transcription of the responses.

Data Processing and Analytical/Statistical Treatment of Data

Since the study employed a convergent-parallel mixed-method design, two separate analyses were conducted before they were integrated to illustrate the relationship between the two datasets. In the quantitative phase, the data were organized prior to the qualitative data analysis by exporting the Excel File from the Google Forms website and downloading a copy of the summary of the responses. The raw data inside the Excel file were labeled according to the SAMR Model to guide the statistician in conducting the statistical analyses. The statistical software that was used was Jamovi, which is free and an open statistical tool.

In treating the quantitative data, descriptive statistics, specifically measures of central tendency and variability, were used to identify the frequency and percentages of the responses. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize and organize the characteristics of the data gathered. Further, central tendency measures estimated a data set's average, while variability examined how the datasets were dispersed or closely tied together. In the study, the mean and standard deviation for every item and each SAMR category were calculated to gauge the extent and illustrate the nature of the use of AI in the research classes.

Additionally, frequency counts and percentages were utilized to assess the responses of the respondents in the Likert scale. Through this, it was illustrated how the respondents agreed or disagreed with each statement. In line with this, to identify the most and least prevalent SAMR categories, a composite mean score for each SAMR category was also computed by averaging the responses to the items in every domain. Consequently, the computed composite means were compared to one another to determine which category was more prevalent compared to the other categories. Through this, the dominant practice in AI Tool Integration was illustrated.

On the other hand, the qualitative data underwent several procedures to shed light on the advantages and disadvantages of the use of AI in research and teaching. In preparing the qualitative data prior to the thematic analysis, AI Transcribe – Voice to Text was used to transcribe the audio recordings of the interview sessions. After the transcription, the interview responses were grouped per question and labeled per participant. This was done to aid the qualitative data analysis.

Afterwards, thematic data analysis examined the interview participants' responses. Thematic data analysis involved closely analyzing the qualitative data and identifying recurring themes. In this approach, the researcher familiarized themselves with the data to aid in the coding process. Once certain words, phrases, or sentences were coded,

themes were formed. The themes were reviewed before they were defined and explained. As mentioned in the research design, the data analysis was inductive, wherein the data determined the themes. Thematic data analysis helped determine the trends and patterns of the opportunities and limitations of using AI in practical research writing. The major and sub-themes were then identified to highlight the advantages and limitations of the integration of AI in practical research writing.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study will investigate the roles of AI-based tools in research writing instruction in the Senior High Schools of Bataan. Specifically, the study will determine the nature of the utility of AI-based tools in the class and the pedagogical opportunities and limitations they present using the SAMR model. The study will primarily look at the teachers' practices in the integration of AI in research writing instruction. It will include their perceived experiences and insights as they used AI in teaching practical research I and II during the first and second semesters of the academic year. Further, its impact on the students will also be given light through the lens of the teacher's experiences and perceptions.

The study will focus on the following AI: ChatGPT, JenniAI, Deepseek, QuillBot, and Grammarly. These AI are mainly used for various writing purposes, which include research writing. Moreover, these AI were selected based on the pre-survey conducted among SHS research teachers in Bataan. The deliberate selection of these particular AI guarantees a targeted study of their influence on improving research writing abilities among Bataan senior high school students.

The primary subjects of the study will be senior high school (SHS) teachers who handle Practical Research I or II in any of the SHS programs among public and private schools in Bataan in the school year 2024-2025. The participants were selected based on the extent of utility of AI-based tools in teaching research writing. Further, the participants must be English language teachers. SHS teachers who have degrees related to language will also be qualified. This will help in gathering insights that depict the interplay of AI and English instruction through research writing. The students will also not be the subject of inquiry; rather, they should only be described by their teachers based on their classroom and online learning interactions.

RESULTS

Roles of AI in the Substitution Category

Table 1 shows an overall mean of 2.30 (SD = 0.95) for the Substitution level, indicating disagreement with the statements related to substituting AI in teaching and learning research.

Table 1. Roles of AI in the Substitution Category

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
I use AI (ChatGPT/Jenni AI/Deepseek) to accomplish tasks more quickly and efficiently.	2.95	0.818	Agree
I utilize AI solely for their intended use or function.	3.06	1.01	Agree
I encourage my learners to use ChatGPT/Jenni AI/Deepseek to understand research concepts and writing skills.	2.12	1.14	Disagree
I use Grammarly/Quillbot to provide instant corrective feedback.	2.63	1.18	Agree
I use AI to automate manual clerical tasks.	2.09	0.996	Disagree
I use AI (ChatGPT/Jenni AI/Deepseek) to design lesson plans.	1.72	0.910	Disagree
I use AI in creating learning materials for the class. (templates and sample paragraphs)	1.94	1.01	Disagree
I encourage learners to use AI for automating clerical tasks in research.	2.23	0.981	Disagree
I encourage the use of AI to replace more traditional learning resources.	1.58	0.682	Strongly Disagree
Overall Mean	2.30	0.95	Disagree

Legend:

1.00–1.75 = *Strongly Disagree*. 1.76–2.50 = *Disagree* 2.51–3.25 = *Agree* 3.26–4.00 = *Strongly Agree*

The Substitution level, with an overall mean of 2.30 (SD = 0.95), shows that the respondents generally disagreed about the potential use of AI for the substitution function. Respondents generally agree that they use AI to accomplish tasks more quickly and efficiently (Mean = 2.95; SD = 0.818) and utilize them solely for their intended use or function (Mean = 3.06; SD = 1.01). They also agree that they use Grammarly/Quill Bot to provide instant corrective feedback (Mean = 2.63; SD = 1.18), highlighting the acceptance of AI for direct, functional replacements of traditional proofreading.

However, there is a clear disagreement on most of the indicators. Teachers disagree with encouraging learners to use AI to understand research concepts and writing skills (Mean = 2.12; SD = 1.14), automating manual clerical tasks (Mean = 2.09; SD = 0.996), designing lesson plans (Mean = 1.72; SD = 0.910), and creating learning materials (Mean = 1.94; SD = 1.01). Most notably, they strongly disagree with encouraging the use of AI to replace more traditional learning resources (Mean = 1.58; SD = 0.682).

Roles of AI in the Augmentation Category

Table 2 shows an overall mean of 2.93 (SD = 0.87) for the Augmentation level, indicating a general agreement with the statements related to augmenting teaching and learning with AI. Educators widely perceive AI as beneficial for enhancing existing practices without fundamentally transforming them.

Table 2. AI for the Augmentation of Learning Experiences

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
I use AI to accomplish a variety of tasks.	3.00	0.791	Agree
I use AI beyond its intended purpose.	2.22	1.01	Disagree
I use AI to customize instruction based on individual student needs	2.91	1.03	Agree
I am not hesitant to use AI to improve the quality of instruction.	3.20	0.712	Agree
I utilize AI to improve the quality of output of the learners.	2.94	0.916	Agree
I employ AI to enhance students' learning.	3.11	0.831	Agree
I use AI to increase student engagement.	2.97	0.790	Agree
I use AI to compensate for my students' limitations in knowledge and competencies.	3.09	0.824	Agree
I use AI to improve the writing skills of my learners.	2.85	0.888	Agree
Overall Mean	2.93	0.87	Agree

Legend:

1.00–1.75 = *Strongly Disagree*. 1.76–2.50 = *Disagree* 2.51–3.25 = *Agree* 3.26–4.00 = *Strongly Agree*

Most indicators show strong agreement. Respondents agree that they use AI to accomplish a variety of tasks (Mean = 3.00; SD = 0.791). They also agree that they customize instruction based on individual student needs (Mean = 2.91; SD = 1.03). AI's ability to provide personalized learning experiences supports this capacity (Bhutoria, 2022). Respondents are not hesitant to use AI to improve the quality of instruction (Mean = 3.20; SD = 0.712). They agree that they utilize AI to improve the quality of learner output (Mean = 2.94; SD = 0.916) and improve learners' writing skills (Mean = 2.85; SD = 0.888). Literature on AI's effectiveness in refining language accuracy supports this (Buriak et al., 2023). Educators also agree that they employ AI to enhance students' learning (Mean = 3.11; SD = 0.831) and use AI to increase student engagement (Mean = 2.97; SD = 0.790). Also, they agree that they use AI to compensate for students' limitations (Mean = 3.09; SD = 0.824). These high means and relatively low standard deviations suggest a consensus among educators that AI effectively enhances various aspects of their teaching and students' learning

Roles of AI in the Modification Category

Table 3 reveals an overall mean of 3.01 (SD = 0.81) for the Modification level, indicating a strong agreement among respondents that AI modify and transform aspects of their teaching and research practices. This suggests that educators are experiencing significant shifts in their pedagogical approaches due to AI integration.

Table 3. AI in the Modification of Teaching Goals and Practices

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
AI significantly change the nature of research teaching.	3.17	0.894	Agree
AI integration results in changes in my role as a research teacher.	3.18	0.768	Agree
AI modifies the learning objectives and activities in the research class.	2.92	0.735	Agree
AI changes the criteria for evaluating the student research outputs.	2.85	0.755	Agree
I prioritize students' ideas and reasoning over technical aspects of the study.	3.28	0.718	Agree
I teach my students how to use AI for research writing.	2.77	0.932	Agree
I am concerned about the potential for AI to encourage academic dishonesty	3.54	0.831	Agree
I allow the collaboration between AI and students in writing major parts of research.	2.57	0.829	Agree
I allow students to take new roles in research writing with the help of AI.	2.82	0.882	Agree
Overall Mean	3.01	0.81	Agree

Legend:

1.00–1.75 = *Strongly Disagree*. 1.76–2.50 = *Disagree* 2.51–3.25 = *Agree* 3.26–4.00 = *Strongly Agree*

All indicators in this category show agreement. Teachers agree that AI significantly change the nature of research teaching (Mean = 3.17; SD = 0.894) and that AI integration results in changes in their role as a research teacher (Mean = 3.18; SD = 0.768). They also agree that AI modifies learning objectives and activities (Mean = 2.92; SD = 0.735) and changes criteria for evaluating student research outputs (Mean = 2.85; SD = 0.755). A high level of agreement is observed for prioritizing students' ideas and reasoning over technical aspects (Mean = 3.28; SD = 0.718), teaching students how to use AI for research writing (Mean = 2.77; SD = 0.932), allowing collaboration between AI and students in writing major parts of research (Mean = 2.57; SD = 0.829), and allowing students to take new roles in research writing with the help of AI (Mean = 2.82; SD = 0.882). The highest mean in this category (Mean = 3.54; SD = 0.831) is for the statement, "I am concerned about the potential for AI to encourage academic dishonesty," indicating a strong agreement with this concern.

Roles of AI in the Redefinition Category

Table 4 indicates an overall mean of 2.60 (SD = 0.86) for the Redefinition level, suggesting a general agreement with statements related to AI's role in redefining teaching and learning. However, this agreement is more nuanced and less pronounced than in the Augmentation and Modification categories, with greater variability in responses.

Table 4. AI for the Redefinition of Research Instruction

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
I use AI to provide entirely new learning experiences for the learners.	2.48	1.06	Disagree
I aim for learning outcomes that are only possible with AI.	2.20	0.833	Disagree
I aim for different learning outcomes.	2.60	0.880	Agree
I utilize AI to invent new ways of performing research-related tasks.	2.86	0.747	Agree
I use AI to create new research-related tasks.	2.65	0.856	Agree
I allow my learners to take on new roles in research writing.	2.97	0.770	Agree
I use AI to introduce new perspectives in research writing	2.54	0.867	Agree
By harnessing AI, I create opportunities for collaborative research projects that span disciplines and geographical boundaries	2.38	1.03	Disagree
AI facilitates the exploration of alternative research methodologies	2.83	0.782	Agree
Overall Mean	2.60	0.86	Agree

Legend:

1.00–1.75 = Strongly Disagree. 1.76–2.50 = Disagree 2.51–3.25 = Agree 3.26–4.00 = Strongly Agree

While the overall mean suggests agreement, several specific indicators show disagreement. Respondents disagree that they use AI to provide entirely new learning experiences for learners (Mean = 2.48; SD = 1.06), aim for learning outcomes that are only possible with AI (Mean = 2.20; SD = 0.833), or create opportunities for collaborative research projects that span disciplines and geographical boundaries (Mean = 2.38; SD = 1.03). Teachers agree that they aim for different learning outcomes compared to traditional teaching (Mean = 2.60; SD = 0.880), utilize AI to invent new ways of performing research-related tasks (Mean = 2.86; SD = 0.747), use AI to create new research-related tasks (Mean = 2.65; SD = 0.856), allow learners to take on new roles in research writing (Mean = 2.97; SD = 0.770), use AI to introduce new perspectives (Mean = 2.54; SD = 0.867), and facilitate the exploration of alternative research methodologies (Mean = 2.83; SD = 0.782).

Pedagogical Opportunities of Using AI

Transcript 1. The Core Functions of AI in Research and Teaching

1. AI as Grammar Checking Assistant

One of the primary functions of AI for research teachers is its utility in ensuring the grammatical accuracy of students' outputs. This includes the evaluation of students' sentence construction, verb tenses, use of conjunctions, punctuation, and proper capitalization. This emerged from the data as participants repeatedly highlighted the use

of AI in checking their students' writing. Although grammar accuracy is not in the curriculum guide for Practical Research I and II, this becomes an implied task for teachers to ensure that students are effectively and clearly wording out their insights and arguments in their papers. With the use of AI, this extra task is alleviated from the teachers, providing opportunities for them to focus on other tasks. For instance, participants mentioned that:

Participant 5 (P5): "On matters of checking for grammar after having constructed the student's manuscript, I used Grammarly."

Participant 6 (P6): "It makes it easier for them to translate their ideas into words."

Participant 7 (P7): "AI-powered tools enhance writing quality by offering grammar and style corrections, improving clarity and coherence."

Participant 12 (P12): "AI help my students in building depth to the statement being written in their paper while ensuring the logical and coherent elements."

The statements above show the varied ways in which teachers take advantage of AI's mastery over grammar. Participants generally expressed that they use AI in the editing and revision phase of the writing process, and not prior to. AI is not used to teach grammar as formal lessons or discussions; instead, it is more of a grammar evaluator tool for the teacher and a practical guide in applying the principles of grammar in the editing process for the students. Nonetheless, educators see the value of AI in that it improves the accuracy of the sentences and enhances the clarity and articulation of ideas - generally raising the bar of what is expected from student writing. Tools such as Grammarly are very much a part of the routine used to give out almost instant responses to mistakes in grammar.

2. AI as an Example and Template Developer

Research papers are highly structured, procedural, and template-specific depending on the research design, so research instructors also put effort into teaching how to write certain parts of the study. This theme shows how AI can generate writing samples or templates of specific parts of the study that can be used as guides or examples for students in the writing process. Since SHS students are new to writing research papers, examples and templates are essential for them to grasp and understand abstract concepts that are presented to them. However, since public SHSs across the country lack access to published studies, teachers use AI to show students examples and provide them with templates.

Participant 2 (P2): "I can prompt it to come up with formats and templates that students can use so they can easily just write their papers. These templates serve as their guide. For my part, it's easier to check their outputs."

Participant 7 (P7): "AI-powered tools assist students in structuring their papers effectively..."

Participant 8 (P8): "It aids in my instruction when making research templates and detailed instructions, which assist learners a lot when dealing with research chapters."

Participant 9 (P9): "I can easily give examples (like research titles) and discuss them with my students."

It is seen from the statements that AI do very well in developing research procedures and in the design of templates that, in turn, better guide students through the research process. Teachers use AI to create a general outline that students can follow and sample parts of the outline, which act as concrete examples that further enhance students' understanding. It acts as the model for the students to follow. This practice of using templates in research paper writing is supported by the study by Syazali et al. (2023), whose experiments suggested that using samples and paper templates are effective methods in teaching the writing of a paper.

3. Fostering Ethical Use of Technology (AI)

This theme illustrates how AI influence the initiative of the SHS teachers to teach ethical ways of using AI in the research writing process. Along with the emergence of AI is the surfacing of threats to academic dishonesty and other unethical uses of AI (Misra & Chandwar, 2023). However, this risk became an opportunity for teachers to start conversations on the ethical ways of using new technology. It became a platform to foster the values of honesty among learners. Teachers highlighted in their statements that:

Participant 7 (P7): "Educators should guide students in distinguishing between AI-assisted writing and their own critical thinking and analysis."

Participant 10 (P10): "Academic integrity and transparency are some of the considerations in using AI."

Participant 11 (P11): "Guiding them and teaching them basic principles in using AI in research writing."

Participant 14 (P14): "They have to learn how to properly utilize these tools without compromising their creativity and critical thinking skills, and I think the school is the best place where they could learn it."

These statements from the participants show their concern and accountability regarding the employment of AI in their classroom. They emphasize the need for explicit instruction and guidance among students on how to properly and ethically utilize AI in the writing process. They also emphasized that critical thinking among students must be preserved, which can be prevented if the students are prevented from misusing the technology. The teachers showed their adaptive tendencies with their statements. Instead of resisting the change and new challenges brought by the technology, they responded by using the same technology as a way to foster integrity among the learners. This aligns with the Unified Theory of Learning with Artificial Intelligence (Gibson et.al, 2023), where AI becomes a catalyst for change in culture. It shapes the norms among teachers of research to teach responsible use among students.

Transcript 2. Benefits of AI-Utility for the Research Teacher

1. Convenience and Efficiency through Automating Tasks

Ultimately, since AI is a master of automation, its utility in the work process makes the majority of the teaching-related tasks less difficult to accomplish. In this sub-theme, the capacity of AI to singlehandedly process data in seconds is highlighted, as it alleviates the teachers' burden of manually attending to their paperwork. Due to this, teachers left favorable statements on the technology, saying:

Participant 6 (P6): "AI help automate or streamline clerical tasks, which makes us work more on teaching and working directly with students."

Participant 7 (P7): "AI streamlines administrative tasks such as grading, scheduling, and organizing research documents, reducing the time spent on paperwork and allowing more focus on student engagement...."

Participant 13 (P13): "It helps me a lot in editing the works of my students. Before, I was spending too much time editing...."

Participant 14 (P14): "It offers convenience and helps me focus on more important tasks at hand, such as focusing on the content of my students' research. I could easily create lesson plans, engaging activities, or even better suggestions just by typing a prompt. It helps me save time and effort."

Efficiency and ease of use were reported by SHS teachers as key benefits of AI, which put an end to long-standing teaching tasks, reduced cognitive load, and increased speed of routine processes. AI help them in their clerical and instructional tasks. There is an emphasis on the reduced time spent working that is attributed to the automation capabilities of AI. They also highlighted the opportunity it provides for them, as they acquire more time to focus on other tasks, which may be work-related or personal.

2. Added Support in Completing Teaching-related Tasks

Beyond what AI do for efficiency, AI acts as an overall support for the teachers in their various tasks. This theme narrates how AI provides overall support for instructional and clerical tasks of teachers. As teachers are expected to prepare lesson plans, develop learning and assessment materials, and provide feedback, AI acts as a personal partner or an assistant to aid them in doing all their tasks. It does not replace them; rather, they work together for a more efficient and less demanding workflow.

Participant 7 (P7): "AI simplifies the assessment process by quickly analyzing students' drafts, providing constructive feedback, and identifying areas for improvement."

Participant 8 (P8): "In instruction, AI supports personalized learning by providing adaptive learning resources, automating assessments, and generating content such as quizzes and research questions tailored to students' needs."

Participant 12 (P12): "AI help me in crafting creative and meaningful activities to deliver complex topics that can easily be grasped by the learners. ..."

Participant 14 (P14): "AI helps both my students, specifically in feedback giving..."

SHS research teachers note that AI allows them to share their workload, which reduces the effort they have to exert in order to complete all of their work-related tasks. AI such as ChatGPT and Grammarly can personalize and develop varied learning experiences for the learners. Manually, it can be too tedious for the teacher. Further, AI can draft, grade assessments, and provide feedback, among other things. This is related to the themes that were explained in the preceding sections regarding the primary functions of AI for teachers. Since AI can generate templates and correct grammar mishaps, they allow for learning personalization through customized templates and feedback.

Transcript 3. AI Aiding the Teaching and Learning Experience

1. Improved Lesson Clarity and Structure

This theme focuses on how AI aids the teacher in clearly communicating the lessons to the students. Teaching and learning research concepts can be overwhelming for both the teacher and the students. There is a tendency for overly abstract instructions that are difficult for learners to grasp. AI helps both parties in solving this problem by ensuring that lessons are clear and arranged in a way that makes it easy for the learners to understand the lessons in the subject.

Participant 2 (P2): "I use it to develop research procedures that are clear and structured, making it easier for students to follow and understand each step of the research process."

Participant 12 (P12): "These help me also to clear the structure of my instructions and guidelines in every task that I want them to comply with."

Participant 12 (P13): "AI take the role of being a compass that guides us in making sure every step of our research writing is on the right track."

Participant 3 (P3): "Using AI in practical research writing enhances both teaching and learning by making research more efficient, structured, and engaging."

The participants agree that AI also make the delivery of the lessons and administration of learning tasks more effective by ensuring that the steps are not confusing to the students. It can be inferred from the responses that AI is used to develop different learning materials, such as handouts and modules, which students directly interact with. The utility of these materials developed with the aid of AI allows for a clear understanding of tasks.

Pedagogical Limitations of AI

Despite the benefits of the integration of AI in research instruction, the qualitative data also reports on issues and problems educators face when they implement AI in research writing instruction. These issues include practical, tech-related, and pedagogical concerns.

Transcript 4. User-Related Issues in Using AI

1. Specificity and Expectations

The first issue in using AI is the interaction between the user and the technology. This theme illustrates how pre-conceived notions translate to ineffective use of AI as a technology. For AI to function properly and accurately provide your target response, it requires specific prompts that provide all the necessary specifications, requirements, parameters, and details. Further, AI can only access a database that was updated at a certain time; hence, it cannot access all the information available on the internet. The problem arises if the user is unaware of these limitations. These can be observed in the statements:

Participant 2 (P2): "You really have to be patient with providing prompts to come up with the answers that you need...make sure that what it offers aligns with your needs."

Participant 3 (P3): "AI sometimes generates false or misleading information, including fabricated references. "

Participant 6 (P6): "You have to double-check the data given by AI. Because sometimes, it gives you false information."

These statements show how certain skills and notions should be possessed by the user to utilize AI properly. Teachers report that AI provides information which are not factual; hence, being critical in evaluating the received information is critical. This is heavily reiterated by the respondents, who unanimously stated that AI should not be taken as it is.

2. Students' Skill Deficiency in Using AI

This theme pictures the lack of students' skills in using AI for their school tasks. Similar to the plight of the teachers, the learners also experience difficulties in using the technology due to their lack of training in using it effectively, as they are still developing competencies to perform such tasks.

Participant 11 (P11): "Most learners do not know how to filter information in AI. It was an expected and observable occurrence."

Participant 12 (P12): "I observe that my students are struggling with the proper usage of AI prompts."

Participant 14 (P14): "Some students were also unfamiliar and not knowledgeable with different AI at first."

The statements above show the different skills that students lack in using AI as an educational tool. Some students are unfamiliar with the tool, while others cannot properly use it or the information it provides. However, it can also be observed that teachers do not claim that all students are incapable; however, it can be inferred that a substantial number of students are unskilled. In this scenario, it can be observed that technology can

only be properly implemented if the teachers can enable their students using the technology as supported by the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2023). The teachers' knowledge of the technology can be a factor in upskilling the students on AI use.

Transcript 5. Technological Issues of AI in the Classroom

This theme looks at what educators deal with when they try to use AI in research writing—technical, financial, and pedagogical issues are included. It delves into the multifaceted challenges educators face when integrating AI into research writing instruction. These issues span technical, financial, and pedagogical domains, highlighting the complexity of adopting AI in educational settings. Central to this theme is the reality that while AI offers promising enhancements to teaching and learning, its effective use is hindered by subscription-based access models, limited infrastructure, mechanistic tool responses, and gaps in user readiness and training.

1. Subscription and Access

Although the majority of AI are readily available online for free, their premium functions are locked, which can only be unlocked by availing subscriptions. However, the majority of teachers and students lack the finances to avail this subscription; hence, only the free-of-use functions are available to them, which are very restrictive or limited in capacity and capabilities. For instance, tools like Grammarly and Quilbot need a subscription for efficient use: Participants expressed that:

Participant 1 (P1): "Premium subscription – Grammarly & Turnitin."

Participant 6 (P6): "Quality AI need payment."

Participant 7 (P7): "Accessibility issues, such as internet dependency and software limitations, can hinder seamless integration into the research writing process, especially in resource-limited settings."

Participant 12 (P12): "The users themselves are not fully aware of maximizing the best things that the available technology has to offer."

The statements above raise concerns about how AI platforms, such as Grammarly and Turnitin, are restricted by subscriptions, which results in disabling most of their users.

2. Mechanical Issues

AI is a highly advanced technological innovation that aids instruction by automation, mass data processing, personalization, and many other methods. However, beyond these capacities is to think exactly like a human being. Regardless of its advancement, it is still only a program that can sometimes be inaccurate, inefficient, or insufficient. This theme highlights how AI can sometimes be too mechanical or machine-like, like in responding to certain prompts. It provides literal or shallow responses when asked about something more personal or critical. As observed in the following statements:

Participant 3 (P3): "AI suggestions may limit personalized or innovative teaching approaches."

Participant 5 (P3): "AI lacks critical thinking and deep contextual understanding of research topics."

Participant 7 (P7): "Providing feedback using AI can be efficient, but it may not always capture the depth of personalized insights that students need for improvement."

Participant 8 (P8): "The answers from ChatGPT are too shallow sometimes. The context is repetitive and does not reflect real-time situations."

Participant 9 (P9): "Sometimes, AI also experiences glitches in the system (ChatGPT). It gives a different answer from the instruction I gave."

The teachers' statements above enumerate the different issues that they have encountered due to the mechanical nature of AI or because it is a machine. They expressed that it lacks the human touch of creating something new, connecting to the person, and thinking outside the box, which are integral to the instructional process. Thus, although it may be able to assist the teachers in the mentioned tasks, it may not be as impactful as intended due to this limitation.

The Effects of AI Integration on the Students

Transcript 6. AI Helping Learners Write Research Papers

1. Enhancing Engagement

Engagement in the instructional process means the student are actively involved and are proactively trying to learn and develop their skills in the subject. It is the presence of motivation within the learners to continue writing their papers. In this theme, the positive effect of AI on student engagement in the lessons and in the writing process of research outputs is explained.

Participant 3 (P3): "Using AI in practical research writing enhances both teaching and learning by making research more... engaging..."

Participant 7 (P7): "AI allows both teachers and students to focus on critical thinking, creativity, and deeper analysis, ultimately improving research quality and engagement."

Participant 12 (P12): "AI help me in crafting creative and meaningful activities to deliver complex topics that can easily be grasped by the learners."

Participant 14 (P14): "It somehow also improves the performance and collaboration of my learners because there is 'something' that can assist them in writing their paper aside from their teacher or Grammarly."

Teachers observed that AI contributes to increased student involvement. AI was described by teachers as a tool that can assist learners in doing tasks independently, which makes them more involved and responsible for their own learning. Information is not solely reliant on the teachers but can be constructed by learners themselves through

their interaction with AI. The statements above suggest that the interactive and adaptive nature of these tools can sustain student interest and participation in research-related activities.

2. Technical Writing Assistance

This theme shows how AI acts as an assistant or guide as they piece their ideas together and put them into writing. In relation to the prior theme, where AI is used to correct grammar, this theme shows the students' side of reaping the benefits from AI. They are not only assisted in grammar, but they are also assisted in the multifaceted aspects of writing. Organizing ideas, paraphrasing claims and arguments from sources, and ensuring the coherence and cohesiveness of paragraphs. AI tools can offer suggestions that help students deepen their critical thinking and improve their academic voice.

Participant 1 (P1): "When it comes to technical writings, student-researchers are guided in doing or writing research. "

Participant 2 (P2): "I just provide them with an AI-generated template which they can follow to write their papers step-by-step."

Participant 3 (P3): "Helps students frame clear and focused problem statements and hypotheses."

Participant 4 (P4): "It gradually helps the students, especially when they lack ideas and comprehensive and critical analysis about their study."

Participant 14 (P14): "The research results in a more refined paper.... they could focus more on the content of the research itself instead of the technicalities. "

Respondents frequently noted that AI helps students address the technical demands of research writing. Their statements suggest that students benefit from structured, AI-supported tools that aid in organizing and improving their writing. The participants highlighted the importance of a gradual and incremental way of teaching, providing students enough time to write different parts of the research papers, ranging from specific parts to overall outlines. It was also noted how AI provides opportunities to focus more on the content of the study, rather than the technical parts.

Transcript 7. Students' Unethical Use of AI

This final theme was formed due to the concern of the teachers about the students' improper use of AI. Students tend to over-reliance on technology, completely disregarding the ethics in using technology and writing research papers. They tend to use AI as their aide in completing their academic tasks in writing and research work.

a. Over-reliance on AI

Students' over-reliance on AI happens when they put all the workload on the technology. They let AI conceptualize, generate, and analyze while they only input the

prompt and copy and paste what has been generated. This also involves the disregard for the accuracy of the content provided by AI.

Participant 1 (P1): "Students solely depend on the AI-generated answers, not thinking that it is obviously copied & pasted..."

Participant 5 (P5): "There were many times that they became very reliant on the information and ready-made responses of the AI, which they often copied and pasted without even reading the content of the material...."

Participant 8 (P8): "AI is reducing students' critical thinking. Most outputs are not revised and are totally pasted in the paper without thoughts of plagiarism. Ethics and academic integrity are forgotten."

Participant 10 (P10): "Students' over-reliance on the tool sometimes leads to dishonesty and skill degradation."

As expressed by the participants, students are directly copying the AI-generated content and pasting it into their papers without noting that it is not their own words. Further, they do not examine the content nor process it, which ultimately defeats the purpose of the learning task. Technology becomes a hindrance to the learners' development of academic skills instead of a support.

Integration of Findings

In integrating the roles of AI and its perceived benefits and limitations, clear relationships between the two findings can be observed. Teachers agreed that the primary roles of AI are as modifiers and enhancers of teaching and learning. Instruction is modified due to the different functionalities and benefits that AI can provide. The technology can work alongside the teacher in assessing and evaluating students' work and in designing lessons and instructional materials. AI also augments instruction since it makes everything efficient through automation, which allows for greater support for the teacher. Thus, it has been shown that teachers have transitioned from knowledge providers to hybrid orchestrators who strategically integrate AI to amplify instruction, personalize learning experiences, and manage new classroom dynamics. AI acts as a teaching partner that can adapt to the students' needs, thus creating a collaborative triad that works together towards achieving a common goal.

Moreover, with the presence of several limitations and challenges to access, security, and accuracy, it was demonstrated that new technology alone does not cause major alterations since external support is necessary to enable teachers to redefine traditional teaching methods in research. The status of teachers, students, and schools in terms of readiness hinders the technology from completely rewriting the status quo in research instruction. In the same way, the limitations discourage teachers from letting AI take over their place. Issues in accuracy and academic dishonesty raise reservations about letting AI complete instructional tasks without human supervision.

DISCUSSION

The Roles of AI in Teaching

Of the four roles of technology in teaching, based on the SAMR Model, AI was found to be inclined to the Modification and Augmentation category. This is supported by the discussions on how AI necessitates educators to adapt their instructional methods and roles, moving towards facilitators of learning rather than sole knowledge providers (Ghamrawi et al., 2023). As they integrate the technology, their roles change as well. The allowance of AI-student collaboration points to a modification of traditional writing processes, where AI can provide automated feedback, enabling teachers to focus on higher-order thinking and content development (Darvishi et al., 2023). In this alteration of research instruction comes the improvement or augmentation of the overall efficiency and effectiveness of the lesson delivery. This efficiency is well-documented in literature, where AI assists with administrative tasks, assessment, and clerical work (Farhan et al., 2024), and generally makes the writing process timelier and more efficient. It can provide personalized learning and refine language accuracy (Bhutoria, 2022; Buriak et al., 2023), which helps the teacher in providing lessons and assistance tailored to the students.

On the other hand, teachers are hesitant to use AI for its redefinition and substitution capacity. This quantitative hesitation is often explained by the current limitations of generative AI, which may still be faulty in analyzing complex research data, synthesizing extensive literature, or producing entirely novel, accurate content without significant human oversight (Dwivedi et al., 2023). Similarly, teachers are only willing to appreciate AI for its basic utility and efficiency in performing specific, defined tasks such as grammar correction. This is consistent with studies showing the effectiveness of grammar and paraphrasing tools in improving the mechanical aspects of writing and saving time for both students and teachers (Alammar & Amin, 2023). However, in terms of fully replacing them, there is a strong reluctance among educators to fully substitute human-led instruction or traditional resources with AI, especially for fundamental learning and complex pedagogical tasks. This reluctance is often rooted in concerns about AI's limitations in fostering critical thinking, deep conceptual understanding, and personalized pedagogical insight (Zhai et al., 2024). Educators recognize that while AI can assist with content generation, it lacks the nuanced understanding and adaptive capabilities required for effective lesson planning and curriculum development (Al-Zahrani, 2024).

Pedagogical Opportunities of Using AI

When it comes to the pedagogical opportunities, limitations, and their effects on the students, the qualitative findings showed that AI should be maximized, but with caution in use. The pedagogical opportunities when using AI show the different ways that it can be used, and their impact to the overall teaching process. Primarily, AI helped in assessing and developing the writing skills of the students. The dominance of the perceived benefits of AI in terms of grammar and writing assistance in the study aligns with similar literature and research. For instance, it was found that the AIs that serve as

writing assistants are the most frequently utilized by educators and learners in research (Del Giglio & Da Costa, 2023).

Further, the consensus of the current study with the prior research attests to the Input Hypothesis by Stephen Krashen and the Scaffolding Theory by Lev Vygotsky. The Input Hypothesis explains that students will acquire and learn the language if the linguistic input provided to them is only a step higher than their current level (Taylor, 2021). This implies that the teacher must consider the students' current level to appropriately supplement the language form that they need. In the same premise, the Scaffolding Theory elaborates that a support or scaffolding must be provided to the students for them to move from one level of competency to another. In this case, AI can readily provide comprehensible input since it can infer from what the student wrote.

This practice of using templates in research paper writing is supported by the study by Syazali et al. (2023), whose experiments suggested that using samples and paper templates are effective methods in teaching the writing of a paper. This is similar to the application of the approach to writing, which is the Genre Approach. In this approach to teaching writing, students are exposed to the characteristics, language features, or styles in writing a specific text type (Dirgeyasa, 2016). The effectiveness of this approach to writing has already been established for its significant impact in improving students' outputs (Galegane & Ntereke, 2022). The only difference in this context is that the provision of the genre samples is mediated by AI, with powers of personalization and contextualization.

Aside from instructional improvement, AI also acts as a support that promotes work efficiency. Celik et al. (2022), for instance, explored the opportunities that AI provides for teachers, which in turn support them in automating their tasks in scoring students' assessments and providing feedback on their output. Farhan et al. (2024) add that AI assists with the administrative tasks and clerical work of the teachers, too. These are just some of the supportive capabilities that AI offers. Through these, teachers can divert their focus and energy to more important tasks in teaching (Huang & Winkel, 2019). Generally, AI improves the work-life balance of teachers through automation. With all of the capabilities of AI aligned with teachers' tasks, the technology proves to be an integral part of the teachers' tools in teaching at the present time.

Pedagogical Limitations of Using AI

In terms of limitations, two categories became prevalent: issues related to the user and problems with the technology itself. For the users, they are limited by their limited understanding of using the technology. With this, the assertion of the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2023) on the importance of technological knowledge becomes relevant. Without sufficient knowledge of the tool, it could possibly become a detrimental part of instruction, which may provide students with incorrect information. The teachers' knowledge of technology can be a factor in upskilling students on AI use. Existing studies show that Filipino students are poor in digital literacy due to disparities in socioeconomic status, limited access to digital tools, insufficient teacher training, outdated education

policies, and various social and cultural influences (Mangarin & Climaco, 2024). This indicates that although students may use AI for simple purposes, their use may not be correct or efficient. To address this, Tate et al. (2023) suggested that teachers should help learners understand how AI works by clarifying where AI obtains content, how it personalizes responses, and what its limitations are. Ultimately, teachers play a crucial role in enabling learners to use the technology responsibly and effectively by integrating AI-use training into classroom instruction.

On the technology's end, access and mechanical issues emerged from the findings. Since most AI tools are internet-based and subscription-dependent, the limited financial capacity of teachers and students restricts access to their full functionality. Poor infrastructure in public schools—such as unstable internet connectivity and a lack of devices (Mangarin & Climaco, 2024)—further affects technology integration. This illustrates how external factors influence the use of technology, extending beyond the TPACK framework (Mishra & Koehler, 2023), which primarily focuses on technological, content, and pedagogical knowledge. In terms of its mechanical issues, AI remains a programmed tool that lacks human-like cognitive and emotional depth. Despite its advanced automation and data-processing capabilities, it often fails to demonstrate critical thinking, contextual awareness, or emotional understanding. Rahman et al. (2023) emphasize the continued importance of human intervention between technology and its users, while Fontanilla et al. (2023) underscore maintaining human connection in the classroom to cultivate students' creativity, critical thinking, and individuality. In essence, AI should be viewed as a supportive tool rather than a replacement for human instruction. Its limitations in personalization and contextual sensitivity affirm the indispensable role of teachers in ensuring meaningful learning experiences.

Effects to the Students

These opportunities and disadvantages affect not only the teachers but also the students. Students benefit from increased engagement and writing assistance in their research subjects. This aligns with the roles of AI in the micro-level of the Unified Theory of Learning with Artificial Intelligence (Mishra & Koehler, 2023), where it states that AI can encourage motivation among learners by reducing frustration, sustaining effort, and building confidence through personalized feedback and adaptive tasks. The use of AI could therefore develop intrinsic motivation for learners to complete their research tasks, making it a significant driving force for students' success. With the developed motivation, AI assists students in organizing ideas, paraphrasing sources, and maintaining coherence and cohesion. It supports the process of writing rather than replacing it, enabling students to focus more on content while still being guided in technical areas. Anik et al. (2023) and Tran (2024) also emphasized that AI improves organization, coherence, and word usage in thesis writing.

However, Fontanilla et al. (2023) cautioned that overreliance on AI may hinder the development of language and writing skills. Students' over-reliance on AI leads to excessive dependence on generated outputs without critical evaluation. This diminishes opportunities for developing cognitive and research-writing skills. Instead of serving as a

support tool, AI becomes a shortcut that undermines academic growth and ethical awareness. This risk in AI integration is prevalent globally (Misra & Chandwar, 2023).

Overall, AI integration exerts a dual impact on students' learning experiences—both facilitative and detrimental. Positively, AI enhances engagement, scaffolds learning, and promotes learner autonomy. However, over-reliance leads to reduced critical thinking, weakened writing ability, and compromised academic integrity. These findings highlight the need for explicit instruction on ethical AI use and the reinforcement of responsible academic practices.

Conclusions

Teachers view AI as a valuable resource for enhancing and modifying current teaching and learning, which in turn improves efficiency, task management, and the quality of what is taught and what students produce. Teachers are open to gradual change and are actively adapting their roles and pedagogical strategies to integrate AI, indicating a shift from traditional methods. At the same time, teachers are very resistant to the full-scale replacement of human-run instruction, basic learning processes, or traditional learning resources by AI. Hence, although teachers are embracing technology, they still hold their positions in the classroom, and they believe that AI is only a tool they use to modify and improve their teaching.

The practice of utilizing AI in the instructional process shows the two sides in every teaching practice: the good and the bad. While AI may offer convenience, support, and improvement to learning practices, it is constrained by certain limitations in its proper use and accessibility. Thus, this generates new roles for teachers, including an innovator who leverages new technology in the classroom to improve learning outcomes, and a guide who ensures that students are adequately equipped to use AI, guided by ethical standards in writing papers. Generally, the successful integration of AI requires a careful balance between the two, demanding that the teacher be adaptable, open-minded, and prudent in the presence of technology.

The integration of the findings on the roles of AI in the classroom and the benefits and limitations that they present further strengthen the idea that teachers are only open to means of integration that are not extremely intrusive. This is why they only prefer to integrate AI through augmentation and modification, where their role as the leading authority in the instructional process is not overly compromised. The inaccuracies and mishaps in functionalities, together with the lack of complete accessibility of the technology, explain this. Thus, it should be a collaboration where AI serves as support to the teacher and student, rather than a complete replacement. AI is used for technical assistance and improved efficiency, while teachers foster critical thinking, ethical behavior, and a deep understanding.

To apply the study's findings, a training plan was developed that targets the identified limitations of AI use while considering the teachers' preferred modes of technology integration. The study's findings highlighted the specific challenges and

needs of Senior High School Practical Research Writing teachers in using AI, including difficulties in crafting prompts, poor writing feedback, ethical concerns, and accessibility issues. These findings were directly translated into a structured training plan aimed at addressing these needs by focusing on improving teachers' competencies, setting realistic expectations, and promoting the ethical use of AI. Therefore, the study's findings served as a critical foundation for tailoring a relevant and comprehensive training program that aligns with the actual instructional challenges faced by teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed: Since AI is already integrated into the teachers' practices, the Department of Education may design the curriculum for the Course of Practical Research I and II, where the use of AI is explicitly incorporated. In this design, activities encourage human-AI collaboration, where teachers and students refine and critically analyze AI outputs rather than simply substituting their work. Teachers must take advantage of the capabilities of AI through NLP to nurture linguistic competencies among the learners. Furthermore, given the high concern for academic dishonesty, lessons on the ethical use of AI will seamlessly fit into the lesson. The department may also provide support in terms of equipment and training. Consequently, it is recommended that SDO Bataan implement the training plan developed through the study. The training will equip the teachers to deliver improved instruction by utilizing the potential of AI. On the other hand, future studies may expand the information regarding the nature of AI integration to foster a better understanding by using different frameworks in technology integration, such as the Technological, Pedagogical, and Content Knowledge (TPACK) Framework or the Replacement, Amplification, and Transformation (RAT) Model. Finally, researchers should conduct in-depth studies over extended periods to investigate the long-term effects of AI use on student writing skills, critical thinking, and academic integrity.

Training Plan

With the findings of the study, a training plan was developed to take advantage of what the study has found regarding the needs of the SHS Practical research writing teachers at the Schools Division Office (SDO) of Bataan. The primary goal of the training is to expand the teachers' competencies in using AI as instructional tools for language education and research instruction and support them with the common issues that they encounter in the utility of the technology. Further, the training duration is sixteen (16) hours or two days' worth of sessions. Each day, a general focus is explored along with its subtopics.

The sessions in the training plan include Understanding AI Capabilities and Limitations, Prompt Crafting for Research Teachers, Exploration of Free and Low-Cost AI, AI's Feedback Tendencies: Considerations for Research Educators, Responsible Use of AI in Instruction, and Promoting Academic Honesty While Using AI. After the conduct of the intensive training, the Education Program Specialists (EPS) and other staff from SDO Bataan are expected to conduct monitoring in the schools' implementation of the

new practice that the teachers learned from the training. This will allow them to provide support to further enhance the teachers' competencies in using AI in research instruction.

Training Matrix

DAY 1: Understanding AI and Its Role in Research Instruction

Time	Topic / Session	Resource Person	Strategy / Method
8:00 – 8:30 AM	Opening Program	SDO Personnel	Opening Ceremony
8:30 – 9:00 AM	Using AI in Research Education: Risks and Benefits	Division Research Coordinator	Lecture/Interactive Discussion
9:00 – 10:30 AM	Session 1: Understanding AI Capabilities and Limitations	Invited ICT/AI Specialist	Lecture/Interactive Discussion
10:30 – 10:45 AM	Break		
10:45 – 12:00 NN	Session 2: Prompt Crafting for Research Teachers	SHS Research Expert	Lecture and Demonstration
12:00 – 1:00 PM	Lunch Break		
1:00 – 2:15 PM	Workshop 1: Writing Prompts for classroom use with AI	SHS Research Expert	Group Work and Presentation
2:15 – 3:00 PM	Session 3: Exploration of Free and Low-Cost AI	Division IT Officer	Tool Showcase and Hands-on
3:00 – 3:15 PM	Break		
3:15 – 4:00 PM	Session 4: AI's Feedback Tendencies: Considerations for research educators	English/Research Specialist	Simulation and Peer Review
4:00 – 4:45 PM	Workshop 2: Customizing AI Feedback	English/Research Specialist	Pair Work and Guided Revision
4:45 – 5:00 PM	Day 1 Synthesis	Emcee/Facilitator	Reflection Sharing

DAY 2: Ethics, Practice, and Application of AI in Research

Time	Topic / Session	Resource Person	Strategy / Method
8:00 – 8:15 AM	Management OF Learning (MOL)	Designated Participants	Group Activity
8:15 – 9:15 AM	Session 5: Responsible Use of AI in Instruction	Ethics Resource Person	Case Scenarios and Role Play
9:15 – 10:00 AM	Session 6: Promoting Academic Honesty	Master Teacher / SHS Lead	Group Output and Discussion
10:00 – 10:15 AM	Break		
10:15 – 11:45 AM	Workshop 3: Drafting AI Use Guidelines for SHS Research	Master Teacher / ICT Officer	Group Drafting and Critique
11:45 – 12:00 NN	Sharing of Outputs	Participants	Presentation
12:00 – 1:00 PM	Lunch Break		
1:00 – 2:00 PM	Panel Discussion: Experiences in Using AI	Selected SHS Teachers	Panel Talk and Open Forum
2:00 – 3:15 PM	Workshop 4: AI Tool Integration Plan	All Facilitators	Action Planning Template
3:15 – 4:00 PM	Presentation of Plans	Participants	Group Presentation
4:00 – 4:45 PM	Commitment Evaluation	Training Team	Pledge
4:45 – 5:00 PM	Closing Program	SDO Personnel	Closing Remarks

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study was written to explore the AI integration practices of SHS teachers in Bataan in research instruction. Every participant was given informed consent and the freedom to withdraw from the study at any point they decide. Further, the privacy of the participants was also protected. On the other hand, all the sources in the discussion of the literature and findings were properly cited to avoid plagiarism. In analyzing the data, the researcher utmost objectivity. Finally, the findings were used for utilized only for research purposes.

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